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The Truth of Reenactments:

Reliving, Reconstructing, and Contesting History in Documentaries on Genocide

Abstract

This article seeks to renegotiate the relationship between reenactment, truth, history, and the archive in documentaries on genocide. It moves away from the common binaries surrounding the supposed creativity and fictionality of reenactments as opposed to the evidentiary and static archive, and instead reads reenactments as facilitating access to truth. Through four case studies of Claude Lanzmann's *Shoah* (1985), Laurence Rees's *Auschwitz: The Nazis and the "Final Solution"* (2005), Rithy Panh's *The Missing Picture* (2013), and Joshua Oppenheimer's *The Act of Killing* (2012), it contends that reenactments in documentaries on genocide problematize the associations of an image's supposed indexical link to a past event with truth. Instead, reenactments confront us with the constructed nature of historical narrative and enable us to see affective, factual, and ethical truths of the past unavailable through the archive.

Keywords: Reenactment, Documentary, Truth, Archive, Genocide, Historical Narrative

Article

In a famous, perhaps infamous, scene in his documentary *Shoah* (1985), Lanzmann has Treblinka survivor Abraham Bomba retell his experiences of cutting Jewish women's hair just before they were gassed to death by the Nazis. Bomba relates these experiences while seemingly innocuously cutting an ordinary customer's hair in a barbershop in Israel. As he keeps trimming the customer's hair in contemporary Israel, his actions begin to take on increasing significance when he informs us of his role as barber in the forced-labour *Sonderkommando* who prepared unsuspecting Jewish women for extermination. His *Sonderkommando* barbering mirrored in his present-day barbering makes Bomba's deeply emotional testimony even more powerful for the implied audience. What Lanzmann does not tell us, however, is that Bomba had retired from his career as a barber, that the barbershop was rented, and that a crew of barbers and customers was hired as extras entirely for the purpose of Bomba's testimony. What is told is true but the circumstances of the telling are not: the barbershop is a reenactment.

Re-enactments are typically used when there is no filmic capture of a historical enactment (Bruzzi 2019, 49). Unlike archival footage, reenactments bear no indexical relationship to the historical event that thereby would vouch for the veracity of what is captured (Nichols 2008, 74). They have the impossible task, in Nichol's words, "to retrieve a lost object in its original form even as the very act of retrieval generates a new object" (2008, 74). Reenactments' lack of a direct causal bond between footage and historical event has led to powerful—and often celebratory—discourses in film scholarship linking reenactments to fiction (e.g. Margulies 2019, 5; Nichols 2008, 73–74; Bruzzi 2020, 3–9; Kahana 2009, 54–55). Given the enormous creative potential of reenactments, it is understandable that critics tend to focus on and praise those reenactments that question, in Bruzzi's words, "the stability and veracity of original enactments" (2020, 209).

And yet, critics seem to endorse reenactments' powers of creative freedom often less than enthusiastically in the case of documentaries on genocide. As if to turn her own words above on their head, Bruzzi prefers the "authentic archive and interviews" in Rees's *The Nazis: A Warning from History* (1998) over his use of reenactments in *Auschwitz: The Nazis and the 'Final Solution'* (2005) (2006, 45–46). In perhaps the most controversial recent case, director Joshua Oppenheimer's reliance on mass murderer's reenactments of their killings in *The Act of Killing* (2012; hereafter: TAOK) has been met critically in academic literature. Many of the film's critics are doubtful about how genuine demonstrations of remorse by perpetrators in the film are, given their otherwise frequent self-serving performances in reenactments throughout the documentary (van Liere 2018; Meneghetti 2016; Tyson 2015; Crichlow 2013; Fraser 2013; Nichols 2013).

These controversial cases thus seem to confirm negatively reenactments' creative powers. The apparent fictional indulgence reenactments afford and their potential to destabilize the "original enactments" seem inappropriate in the face of mass atrocity—especially when the original enactment of the crime has not received due historical attention (as in the case of the Indonesian 1965-66 mass killings in TAOK). Documentary's power, after all, derives from its ability of "representing reality" with an emphasis on the latter word (Nichols 1992). If reenactments, in turn, are often "associate[d]" with "fiction" (Nichols 2001, xi), we may ask, how do reenactments serve the depiction of reality if they construct the reality they represent? This question is particularly ethically charged, especially in the context of representing mass atrocity: what notions of truth and ethics underlie the use of reenactments in representing genocide?

In what follows, I will examine four different forms of reenactment in documentaries on genocide that are either representative of certain trends in or exemplary for their unusual use of reenactments in documentaries on genocide and provide unique answers to the relation between reenactment and truth, particularly from the 1980s onward.¹ Two of them, *Shoah* and *Auschwitz*, are on the Holocaust, Rithy Panh's *The Missing Picture* (2013) is on the Cambodian genocide, and Oppenheimer's TAOK is on the Indonesian 1965-66 genocide. *Shoah* is perhaps the most discussed of these documentaries and has had a substantial influence on subsequent documentaries on genocide and their reception by critics.² *Auschwitz*, on the other hand, is representative of what is, at least in terms of number, the dominant form of documentary representation of genocide (especially the Holocaust): television productions that are distributed to inform a mass audience of the history of a genocide. Both Panh's and Oppenheimer's documentaries merit closer examination for their particularly innovative use of reenactments that enable us to see yet more ways in which reenactment, history, archive, and truth are entangled.

My discussion will move away from the common binaries surrounding the supposed creativity and fictionality of reenactments as opposed to the evidentiary and static archive. Neither are reenactments instable, fictional (re-)creations that place "in abeyance" what is real (as Kahana suggests, citing Hayden White: 2009, 54–55), nor are archives merely unchanging aggregates of material. Archival material is shaped by the historical circumstances at the time of making but also continues to undergo resignification in being shown in continually renewed contexts – "[n]o archive without outside" as Derrida says (Derrida 1995; see also: Bruzzi 2020, 39). Archival footage or stills

¹ For a highly instructive discussion of the use of reenactments in very early films (including war films) which is distinct from the more recent use of reenactments discussed here, not least because the former were dominantly considered fakes by contemporaries, see (Slugan 2019, 87–139, esp. 105–14).

² The influence of Lanzmann on Panh is discussed by Cazenave and acknowledged by Panh himself (Cazenave 2018, 54; Panh and Bataille 2011, 76). Oppenheimer also discusses Lanzmann (Lusztig and Oppenheimer 2013).

may once have signified the triumph of genocidal ideology, but can be re-contextualized to undermine that ideology, and reenactments, as we will see, can play an integral role in supplementing or undermining (e.g. in the case of propaganda) the original purpose of archival footage. I am thus sympathetic to Bruzzi's critical reevaluation of the typically assumed hierarchy of truthful archive over supposedly fictional reenactment, but I will reject her more radical conclusions of the "fluidity and instability of truth" (2020, 3). Despite the constructed character of reenactments, none of the cases of reenactment I will discuss are fiction—in fact, generally very few reenactments are (Slugan 2021, 116–17; *The Routledge Handbook of Reenactment Studies* has entries on "authenticity," "documentary," and "evidence", but not on "fiction": Agnew, Lamb, and Tomann 2019). That documentaries on genocide pursue a conception of "truth" is unsurprising: what is more surprising, as I will show, is that reenactments play an integral part in conveying truth. These notions of truth vary depending on the narrative strategies of the documentary and can oppose or support the archive. Despite their different forms, they share the fundamental documentary pursuit of convincing the viewer to "accept its world as actual" (Nichols 2001, 2). Yet, the truths these documentaries pursue are not always only epistemic, about how things are or were, but affective, by giving a sense of the trauma and suffering from the atrocity, and ultimately ethical, in the explicit or implicit evaluation of what constitutes an appropriate representation of the atrocity. Reenactments are integral in accessing these truths.

Reenactments as affective reliving

Reenactments offer the opportunity to relive the past (Agnew 2007). Unsurprisingly, thus, one of the paradigmatic cases of reenactments in documentaries on genocide is when they are used to let the viewers share in traumatic experiences of the past. An early and seminal film to do this is Lanzmann's *Shoah*, whose use of reenactments creates a commemorative space in which the viewer and Holocaust survivor affectively partake in the experience related through the testimony. Lanzmann's film centers on the individuality of the witness, almost entirely eschewing archival footage, voice-over commentary, and captions (excepting the opening of the film and the brief introduction of its interviewees throughout the film), among other dominant documentary conventions. Consequently, Lanzmann rejects the label "documentary" for his film (Lanzmann, Larson, and Rodowick 1991, 96), is strictly opposed to seeing in his film any form of generalized transmission of historical knowledge (Hirsch 2003, 70; Felman 1991, 47; Lanzmann, Larson, and Rodowick 1991, 82), and generally believes the historian's endeavor to understand the Holocaust to be obscene (2011a, 385–86).

Despite Lanzmann's resistance to these conventional categories of understanding and knowledge, he abides by a quite strict, mostly implicit, set of standards expressed and measured in the traditional vocabulary of truth (Lanzmann 2011b, 414; 2010, 100). For instance, Lanzmann refuses his camera operator's suggestion to shoot the village of Chelmno from a helicopter (in order to capture its small size), because "There were no helicopters for the Jews" (Lanzmann, Larson, and Rodowick 1991, 94). The camera thus is to follow mimetic principles and to take narrative viewpoints that could have been, and perhaps were in fact, occupied by Jews, especially when shot on locations of the camps. Similarly, Lanzmann rejects his own "acting" in the film as not only false but also a moral failure when he feigns unawareness about the fact that trains were pushed not pulled in Treblinka (Lanzmann, Larson, and Rodowick 1991, 90).

The standards of truth implied by *Shoah*, however, are complicated by Lanzmann's own remarks about *Shoah*'s creating "fictions of the real" (cited and discussed in Saxton 2008, 38) and the fact

that the survivors had to become actors in his reenactments (Lanzmann 2011b, 419; LaCapra 2007, 213). How are we to reconcile Lanzmann's rejection of his own acting with his endorsement and facilitation of survivors' acting? Furthermore, how is the pretense of the barbershop commensurate with any notion of "truth" in *Shoah*? While there is no question of confusing Bomba's haircutting in the Israeli barbershop with his haircutting in Treblinka, the implied audience gets few clues about the barbershop's status as reenactment (LaCapra, for instance, notes that the "viewer is, I think, shocked in learning that the barbershop was rented" (2007, 192)), and yet what troubles Lanzmann more is the pretense of his own acting rather than that of the barbershop.

Clearly, the "acting" Lanzmann requires of Holocaust survivors is different from his own. The "authenticity" Lanzmann seeks is the irreducibly individual, emotive response of the survivor—an individuality the Nazis had denied. Lanzmann's own obsession with reliving Holocaust survivors' personal history (2011b, 419), to share their suffering by suffering himself during the filming (2011c, 403), and to enable an affective-empathetic transfer from testifying survivor to viewer (2011b, 419), suggests that Lanzmann's film becomes truthful precisely in the reliving, rather than a mere recounting, of the survivors' traumatic past. The activation of the imaginary through reenactment is to create a space "where something could happen" (Lanzmann, Larson, and Rodowick 1991, 95). And precisely at the point where such a happening, so to speak, overtakes the mere retelling of testimony and the survivor's emotions surge up, the "boundary between art and life collapses" and "trauma is relived" (LaCapra 2007, 202–3). Avowing the sincerity of Bomba's emotions, Lanzmann expresses his great relief that he had switched tapes just before Bomba's emotional climax in the barbershop, because "It would have been impossible to ask him, 'Please cry again...'" (Lanzmann, Larson, and Rodowick 1991, 95). The tears running down Bomba's face—visually and emotionally magnified in Lanzmann's use of zoom—are genuine (Prager 2020, 292–93).

But why aren't we more troubled by Lanzmann's narrative trickery in the barbershop and why does Lanzmann not explicitly alert us to the status as reenactment? In keeping with his restrained attitude towards captions or other documentary devices of general information conveyance, he could have shown the setting up of the barbershop scene in a similar vein as with the clandestine taping of Suchomel, a former SS-officer at Treblinka. Lanzmann's breaking the fourth wall by showing the secret cameras trained on Suchomel who otherwise has every reason to lie were he filmed by normal means convinces the audience that they are seeing the "real" Suchomel (Kerner 2011, 17). Yet, showing the constructedness of the barbershop setting (aside from creating undue formal parallels between scenes of a perpetrator and his victim), would have removed the viewer from the affective immediacy of Bomba's trauma, possibly even casting doubt on his testimony, at a moment during which Lanzmann wishes the viewers to compassionately live and suffer through the experience with Bomba (Lanzmann 2011c, 403). The barbershop works so effectively as a setting to immersively frame (for the audience) and evoke (for Bomba) the trauma of testimony that it is not Lanzmann's withholding the full information from the audience with which critics typically take issue but rather his relentless probing of the clearly distraught Bomba (Saxton 2008, 36–37). In other words, it's not the pretense of the circumstances of the telling—the uncertain status of the false barbershop for the audience—critics call into question but rather that the pretense works too well in unburying a traumatic past and re-traumatizing the survivor (and perhaps traumatizing the viewer exposed to this eventuation of survivor trauma). Lanzmann's reenactment derives its power over the viewer precisely from our unawareness of its status as construction through which we experience the emotional truth of what happened to Bomba with empathetic immediacy.

Lanzmann's powerful use of reenactments to elicit and relive traumatic experiences has become a paradigmatic case for documentaries on genocide. Exemplary are Panh's *S-21* (2003; Boyle 2009;

Panh and Oppenheimer 2012) and Oppenheimer's TAOK, where reenactments also play a role in accessing the trauma of genocidal perpetrators—though I will argue this is not their primary function in TAOK. Undoubtedly, in both cases, the perpetrator reenactments are not supposed to evoke a similarly compassionate response by the viewers as in the survivor reenactments in *Shoah*. Nonetheless, these reenactments act as an affective and traumatic reckoning of the perpetrators with the truth of their violent former selves and—on a more symbolic level as the reenactments unfold before the viewers—the respective nation's lack of engagement with the past in the present.

Reenactments reconstructing historical truth: supplementing the archive

The cases of reenactment discussed so far derive their affective power over the viewer from the particular individuality of the reenactors who—as survivors (or perpetrators) of genocide—breathe life into the reenactments. Thus, Lanzmann describes *Shoah* as an “incarnation in truth,” a reliving of history in the present that is only possible through (re)staging, not archival images (my translation: Lanzmann 2011b, 414). Characterized in this way, reenactments are fundamentally at odds with archival images, which seemingly merely display the past-ness of the past.

Lanzmann is not the only one to see an implicit opposition between archive and reenactment. Such an opposition is also operative when documentary scholars classify “realist” reenactments as “dramatizations” (Nichols 2008, 84) that are typically “used to heighten and render more accessible the latent drama of the documentary situation” (Bruzzi 2006, 46). The implication is that these types of reenactments (which use actors) keep the viewer in suspense and hence re-present the past, whereas archival footage remains in the past. Since the turn of the millennium, this type of reenactment has been increasingly used by documentaries produced for television, especially those commissioned by public broadcasters (Bruzzi 2006, 43–46; Chatman 2007, 13–33). Yet because these documentaries are often made in the “expository mode” (Nichols 2001, 33–34 & 105–9) and thus attempt to convey a narrative of objective history and truth, it seems that these dramatic reenactments are fundamentally at odds with the documentary's overall purpose: If reenactments serve to create drama and appeal to the viewers' emotions, how does this square with the pedagogical objective to convey historical truth?

Undoubtedly, there is often a perceptible dialectic between the scenes selected for reenactments—due to their dramatic potential to grip the audience—and the distancing tone of the authoritative voice-over commentary talking about the past. Although *Hitler's Henchmen* (1996-1998), produced by the German public broadcaster ZDF, uses reenactments sparingly, when it does it selects scenes with highly dramatic content, such as Rudolf Hess's parachute jump or Martin Bohrmann's attempt to flee in the final battle over Berlin. This dialectic bears its own risks when, for instance, *Hitler's Circle of Evil* (2018)—despite its overt disavowal of the perpetrators as evil through its voice-over commentary—uncritically succumbs to the fascination of its “evil” main characters in its reenactments where, set to quasi-Wagnerian musical pomp, the viewers repeatedly find themselves sharing the thrill with the perpetrators if, say, their 1923 Munich Putsch will be successful.

However, to consider expository documentaries' use of reenactments as merely a question of balancing the scales between drama and archival history is too simplistic. In fact, these reenactments need not be at odds with the overall documentary purpose of conveying historical truth and they are not merely reducible to drama. An early example of reenactments for purposes of historical illustration—and providing legal evidence against the Nazis at Nuremberg—is concentration and extermination camp liberation footage, especially Soviet footage of the liberation

of Majdanek and Auschwitz (1944 and 1945, respectively), where, for example, survivors were lined up behind barbed wire fences and awaited their liberators with muted expressions or were asked to reenact the crowded conditions in the barracks (Hicks 2012, 157–85). Soviet filmmakers contemplated including further reenactments with rejoicing survivors in the footage, but ultimately rejected these as being too far from the truth, since “liberated inmates could hardly stand, let alone jump for joy” (Hicks 2012, 180).³ A more recent exemplary case of reenactments for purposes of reconstructing historical events and educating the public is Laurence Rees’ *Auschwitz*, produced by the BBC in 2005 (for its pedagogical mission, see the educational material on its website “Auschwitz: Inside the Nazi State | PBS” n.d.). *Auschwitz* uses reenactments for purposes of reconstructing a historical event whose archival documentation is missing.

Remarkably, given that the Nazi-regime is otherwise so forthcoming with (propagandistic) images, its perpetration of the Holocaust is largely imageless (Saxton 2008, 46–48). While a number of photos and film footage exists and is shown in *Auschwitz* (and numerous other Holocaust documentaries) of *Einsatzgruppen* killings, such as the photos taken by Wehrmacht soldier Otto Schroff of the Ponary massacres nearby Vilnius or film footage by Walter Frenz of massacres in Liepāja, Latvia, no known footage of gas vans or gas chambers in operation at the extermination camps exists,⁴ most extermination camps were fully destroyed, and although documents exist, communications and meetings about the extermination efforts were conducted in secret and visual records of any kind are exceedingly rare. Considering the unprecedented scale of the Holocaust, the paucity of documents, notes, and commands that reveals a clear chain of command as well as the clear intentions of the perpetrators is surprising (Browning 2007, 10–11; Longerich 2016; Kershaw 2009, 60–118).

Certainly, reenactments are not absolutely necessary to fill these filmic gaps. Other documentaries use interviews or archival footage (largely shot by perpetrators or complicit participants in the Nazi regime) to supplement their voice-over narration. Rees’ earlier *Warning from History* often showed various incriminating documents tumbling onto a stylized desk to a gloomy score. However, the reenactments allow *Auschwitz* to develop a historical narrative in ways that interviews and archival footage cannot. *Auschwitz* makes the escalation of the Nazis’ extermination policies unfolding via backdoor meetings, secret commands, and local and global as well as concerted and improvised efforts of various Nazi officials uniquely clear by reenacting them. Although dramatization was part of the appeal of using reenactments to reach a younger audience—not least in the restaging of Kazimierz Piechowski’s daring escape from Auschwitz—the reenactments perform more than this ancillary role and are integral to what we could call the documentary’s historical method.⁵ They represent what archival propaganda footage of ghettos, Nazi marches or footage of documents not only do not represent but also what they would misrepresent were they to be used instead of reenactments: the surprising informal and unwritten nature in the escalation of the Nazis’ extermination program. In this light, the great verisimilitude between the professional actors and their historical counterparts, the close attention to factual detail (such as Himmler’s SS-1 licence plate), and the use of original languages in the reenactments even down to the Slavic accent (in German) of Slovakian prime minister Vojtech Tuka (played by Polish actor Włodzimierz Press) when

³ The reenacted scenes, however, are not clearly labeled or visually distinct from the non-reenacted ones. Thus one might arguably also speak of fakes, although the circumstances that are reenacted can hardly be considered historically untruthful.

⁴ There is, however, footage believed to be of early gas chamber experiments (with exhaust gas) on Nazi-occupied Soviet territory, which is shown in *Auschwitz*.

⁵ One somewhat uncalled for dramatic device at the end of the third episode of *Auschwitz* is the introduction of Josef Mengele to Höß (and the audience) in Bond-like fashion: “Mengele, Josef Mengele”.

meeting with the German SS-captain Dieter Wisliceny in Bratislava 1942 to discuss the fate of the Jews in Slovakia are not merely historical accounting. The cumulative effect of the reenactments shows the Holocaust's unfolding through meetings, orders, and other communications at local and global levels. This informal and incremental portrayal of the Holocaust's perpetration visually (re)constructs what is now perhaps the most widely accepted historical interpretation of the Holocaust (Longerich 2016; Browning 2007; Kershaw 2009; Kershaw and Browning were advisors on the docuseries. Rees emphasizes their views on the docuseries' website: "Auschwitz: Inside the Nazi State | PBS" n.d.).

The reenactments' function to reconstruct history is also enforced at a formal level. Frequently, reenactments are preceded or followed by archival footage, photos, and copies of documents (where they exist). For instance, Himmler's arrival for a visit at Auschwitz is reenacted and seamlessly followed by existing archival photos of Himmler's visit of the IG Farben complex there. Similarly, we hear excerpts of Höß' memoir being read in voice-over while actor Horst Günter Marx, who plays Höß, acts out what is read. Although the reenacted footage always clearly stands out visually from any archival footage by its more natural (although muted) colors and higher resolution,⁶ the seamless transitions between archive and reenactment suggest that, notwithstanding their *ontological* difference, acknowledged via their noticeable difference in style, there is little *factual* difference insofar as both foster historical understanding.

Auschwitz's reenactments are clearly committed to a notion of historical truth that seeks to make the Holocaust interpretable by supplementing gaps of the visual archives—a commitment that is ultimately an ethical one. This commitment to facticity means the documentary largely refrains from facile demonization of the perpetrators (unlike e.g. *Hitler's Circle of Evil*), but it occasionally utilizes reenactments as a subtle means to create moral contrast. When *Auschwitz* informs the audience about Höß's relief that his deputy Karl Fritzsche had thought of killing—at the time Russian POWs, and later Jews—with Zyklon B gas, a method Höß deemed more humane (see 1998, 188–90), *Auschwitz* uses reenactments for contrast. Höß's relief over the newfound method of killing is narrated via voice-over while we see, in crass contrast, a reenacted scene of domestic harmony with Höß surrounded by his children. This juxtaposition thus gives us a sense of the pedestrian normality of killing for the Nazi perpetrators, a problem contemplated and solved in homely surroundings like any other. While this contrast does not imply moral condemnation as such, the implication for the audience is clearly to realize that such a degree of dehumanization of Jews next to the mundane humanity of this perpetrator's family life is objectionable.

Ethical commitments also become apparent in what *Auschwitz* does not reenact, namely killings of any kind. We do not see actors playing SS-men rounding up other actors playing Jews, nor do we see the ensuing executions reenacted.⁷ Though explicit depictions of killings—often by guns (e.g. in *Schindler's List*, 1993), much more rarely by gas (*Kornblumenblau*, 1989)—are common in fiction films, reenactments of genocidal killings in Rees's *Auschwitz*, like most documentaries, do not exist (Storeide 2012, 263). Instead, *Auschwitz* shows archival footage of Einsatzgruppen shootings in the dunes of the beach of Liepāja (a common staple of Holocaust documentaries), archival photos, or the rare existing footage from early gassing tests on Soviet territory and reframes their original

⁶ Storeide erroneously believes the reenactments are black and white and therefore hard to distinguish from archival footage (2012). For a contrary opinion, apart from my own, see Kerner (2011, 183).

⁷ There is a small exception after the interview with the perpetrator Hans Friedrich, when we see actors representing perpetrators lining up for a mass execution, followed by a close-up of a bolt-action rifle being loaded, and then a camera-shot and dampened sound of cartridges falling down. Yet, neither the act of shooting nor even the sound of a shot is reenacted.

purpose of, for example, signaling perpetrators' triumph to become evidence of atrocity. Thus, whereas *Auschwitz* makes use of archival footage of perpetrator actions and meetings where it exists and otherwise draws heavily on reenactments to fill archival gaps, it does not treat Nazi killings in the same way. To create a reenacted account of Nazi killings would mean either (1) to have actors play known victims—just as actors are playing known, deceased perpetrators—or (2) to let actors play fictional victims. Either case, I believe, would transgress *Auschwitz's* implicit ethics. The second case would fictionalize the killings to a degree incompatible with the documentary's general expository format and its otherwise extraordinary attention to factual detail. It would also kill victims without the opportunity—as happens extensively in fiction film—to build characters whose eventual deaths allow for meaningful, empathetic identification by the implied audience. In the first case, if known victims were played by actors, these victims would effectively die again for dramatic effect. In either case, reenactments of the killings would seem to breach a fundamental ethical norm: If reenactments suggest an iterability “for that which belongs to the singularity of historical occurrence” (Nichols 2008, 79), in avoiding the reenactment of killings *Auschwitz* recognizes the singularity of Holocaust victims' suffering. Therefore, while the reenactments in *Auschwitz* fill gaps in the available archival footage in their quest to convey historical truth, not all gaps in the archive are treated the same way. To convey the perspective of the victims, *Auschwitz* prefers the survivors' oral testimony to reenactment. Although *Auschwitz* and *Shoah* share an ethical commitment to victims and survivors, their commitment manifests itself radically differently in their use of reenactments. Where Lanzmann's concern for victims draws on reenactments to achieve the greatest “incarnation of truth” precisely in those moments in which survivors relive their suffering most closely, *Auschwitz* respect for the victims' eschews reenactments of victims' suffering. *Auschwitz's* reenactments thus reveal their ethical commitments as much in what they show as in what they do not. The documentary's reenactments enable its effort to follow truthfully the currently established interpretation of the Holocaust's incremental stages. At the same time, the documentary's refraining from reenacting killings avoids gratuitously dramatic re-victimizations and acknowledges the uniqueness of the crime.

Untruthful archive, truthful reenactments

While *Auschwitz* faces the scarcity of images of the Holocaust by supplementing the archive through reenactments, Panh's *The Missing Picture* employs reenactments to oppose the archive. Using dioramas with hand-carved clay figurines Rithy Panh tells his personal story of surviving, unlike most of his family, the Khmer Rouge genocide. Archival films of the Khmer Rouge period consist effectively entirely of propaganda footage. Thus, the suffering Panh shows in his reenactments is juxtaposed with the starry-eyed propaganda and “suggest[s] that this archival footage is itself full of missing images” (Barnes 2016, 203) and “deconstruct[s] the lies of [propagandistic] images” (Phay 2021, 205).

Yet, however suggestive such a binary of archive versus reenactment may be, the discussion of reenactments in *The Missing Picture* is complicated by the fact that the Khmer Rouge archival footage is ultimately itself a form of reenactment.⁸ The voice-over commentary asserts on several occasions that we can understand the Khmer Rouge only through their images and that the Khmer

⁸ Thus, I do not fully agree with Barnes that the juxtaposition between Panh's reenactments and state propaganda “effectively subvert[s] the relationship between the authentic and the fabricated, claiming a genuineness for the clay figurines and clips of feature films from the 1960s that is denied the Khmer Rouge,” insofar as there is little that is “authentic” about the propaganda to begin with (2016, 203).

Rouge revolution is nothing but images—images that show a reality according only to their desires.⁹ Khmer Rouge images are a construction. But it is not the constructedness of these images per se that poses a problem for Panh, not least since his dioramas are themselves just that. However, the constructedness of the film's images—propaganda or dioramas—does not mean that all “images are addressed as a problem” and that “any image, whatever its source, ends up raising skepticism and mistrust,” as Sánchez-Biosca claims (2018, 158). Even if the film continually expresses reservations about its images, not any two images in the film are created equal. Nowhere is this clearer than in Panh's continual confrontation of the propaganda through his reenactments.

Panh's reenactments confront Khmer Rouge propaganda in two main ways: (1) They display the suffering the propagandistic stagings absence, and (2) they reveal a form of individual, imagined reality of the narrator that is a more truthful representation of life under the Khmer Rouge—not least in its ethical and emotional considerations—than the archival footage.¹⁰ Thus, Panh's figurines starve and die, whereas the propaganda footage shows supposed surplus harvests and sacks of rice. Panh shows a diorama of an execution, whereas no known archival footage of Khmer Rouge executions exists, despite Panh's efforts to find it (Cazenave 2018, 52). Reenactments allow Panh to reimagine a more dignified end of his father. When his father dies from refusing to eat his degrading diet, we see a brief glimpse of the burial as it happened—his father is wrapped in a metal sheet and thrown into a pit grave by figurines in black uniforms—followed by his mother's description of how he would and should have been buried. Her “burial in words” is an “act of resistance,” as the narrator asserts, which Panh consequently reenacts with images that in turn defy the Khmer Rouge's visual doctrine: the figurines attending the funeral this time are dressed in white (the traditional color of mourning in Cambodia) and pay his father their respects. Even while the images of his father's burial are repeated several times in the film, suggesting that the mourning process is never concluded (Morag 2020, 34; Cazenave 2018, 45), this continual attention of the repeat-burials to the individual person of his father contrasts markedly with the mass graves of the Khmer Rouge. This acknowledgement of and emphasis on personal dignity in life and death is underpinned by an ethics of *individuality* that permeates all of Panh's reenactments and is opposed to the propaganda footage of busy throngs of people subject to a *collective* purpose.

Crucially, Panh's reenactments not only differ from the propaganda in *what* they show but also in *how* they show. The individuality of the figurines is not only conveyed in the telling of individual fates over and apart from that of the uniformed collective, but also in how this telling is managed. Panh's reenactments are full of close-ups and medium range shots of individual figurines, their gestures, expressions, and actions, whereas the distant shots of workers in propaganda turn their subjects into a collective mechanism. Panh's ethics also pervades the organization of his images. While Panh's documentary ultimately follows a linear chronological structure, he nevertheless embraces the fragmentary nature of individual images in the editing and multimedial presentation of his narrative as well as the continuous questioning of the purpose of his images. The ostensible construal of Panh's reenactments—on several occasions we see the figures being carved or the backdrop of the set, precluding any illusionistic immersion by the viewer—self-reflexively forecloses the finality of a conclusive reading in stark contrast to the ends-based ideological interpretation of images in Khmer Rouge propaganda. The propagandistic images fall under a singular interpretive dictate, whereas Panh's images invite the audience to participate in the interpretive process and also point to what may have been excluded from the images.

⁹ My paraphrase of the spoken French in the film: “on comprends les Khmers rouges en observant leurs images,” “Pol Pot forge une réalité conformant à son désir,” “elle [la révolution] existe que comme image.”

¹⁰ Yael Hersonski's documentary *A Film Unfinished* achieves very similar effects as Panh without the use of reenactments by having survivors watch and testify against the stagings of Nazi propaganda footage of the Warsaw ghetto for which Nazis had forced Jews to perform supposed scenes from daily life in the ghetto (Hersonski 2010).

The difference between the two viewing modes of propaganda and Panh's reenactments becomes perhaps most apparent when one is turned into the other. About halfway through the documentary, Panh transforms propaganda footage of a reservoir being dug (already shown earlier), with its purpose of glorifying the progress brought by the revolution, into a reenactment by superimposing a camera-holding figurine onto the footage. Panh thereby exposes the hidden construal and selectiveness of the ideological footage. Furthermore, in a form of climactic progression, this propaganda footage returns once more later in the documentary and this time Panh's alter ego, embodied by a figurine with a colorfully dotted shirt (contrasting with the mandated black of Khmer Rouge uniforms), is superimposed with a deeply concerned facial expression, inviting a different gaze on and interpretation of the propaganda footage that exposes the suffering concealed by the footage. The figurine's look straight at the audience in this scene in which "we cannot suppress our status as spectators" (according to Aaron's notion of "self-reflexive films," 2007, 94) urges us to self-reflexively examine our own gaze and to distance ourselves from the propagandistic spectacle. Panh's organization of images and the self-conscious gaze invited by the reenactments alert us to the fact that the truth of an image is determined not by its indexical relationship to the event it displays but by the structure of its narrative and its attention to the suffering of individuals.

Although both *Auschwitz* and *The Missing Picture* use reenactments to fill gaps in the archive, Panh's reenactments approach the representation of genocide very differently from those of *Auschwitz*. Where the goal of *Auschwitz's* reenactments was to serve the historical interpretability of the Holocaust, Panh's reenactments in their self-reflexivity—while not fundamentally declaring the impossibility of its endeavors—probe the very possibilities of representing and interpreting the Cambodian genocide. Panh's response, not dissimilar to Lanzmann's approach in *Shoah*, is an increased focus on the individual's suffering. Yet, his use of dioramas and figurines establishes a greater affective distance between viewers and reenactments. *The Missing Picture* has no equivalent shot to Lanzmann's zooming in on Bomba's tears. Nonetheless, in both Lanzmann's and Panh's films reenactments enable an access to truths unavailable through the archive. The testimonies and reenactments in *Shoah* give the viewer emotive access to the past in the present, whereas Panh's reenactments assert their truthfulness in their challenge of the archive's narrative. In Oppenheimer's TAOK, we will encounter a similarly radical problematization of historical narrative by exposing its—especially ethical—falsity through its re-creation in reenactments.

Untruthful reenactments, untruthful history

Like Panh's *Missing Picture*, Oppenheimer's TAOK establishes a normative distance to perpetrator images through self-reflexivity. However, unlike in Panh's documentary the self-reflexivity does not arise from the reenactments themselves, but through TAOK's framing of these reenactments. TAOK's reenactments break with several of the conventions and their implicit ethics we established in the previous discussions. The killings in TAOK are reenacted in gory detail and, since it is the perpetrators of the 1965-66 Indonesian mass killings of supposed communists that direct these reenactments, they liberally indulge in representing their view on their murders, reiterating the national Indonesian narrative of glorifying the killers and emphasizing the necessity of the genocide. The perpetrators liberally embellish their reenactments of killings by donning cowboy hats and swinging lassos or filming them in a crime-noir style, inspired by their own favorite movies, and publicly boast about their murderous accomplishments in front of rolling cameras.

Unsurprisingly given their provocative nature, the reenactments' (supposedly) fictional nature plays a central role in most critics' appraisals of the film. While some praise the film's use of fictionalizations (Iversen and Nielsen 2016, 257; Nagib 2016, 221), another strand of film critics expresses serious concerns over the film's truthfulness overall (Fraser 2013, 22; Godmilow 2014;

Nichols 2013, 29) and, in particular, doubts the credibility of protagonist and murderer Anwar Congo's eventual redemption given his unreliable reenactments (van Liere 2018, 32; Meneghetti 2016, 46–47; Tyson 2015, 191; Crichlow 2013). In this view, praise or condemnation—a judgment that is ultimately ethical—of the film would seem to hinge on the provision of an authoritative and corrective narrative by the film (alleviating Fraser, Godmilow, and Nichols's issues) and a credibly genuine redemption by Congo (addressing van Liere, Meneghetti, Tyson, and Crichlow's problems). However, a fact-driven voice-over narrative with a corrective historical account and evidentiary support by the archive in the style of *Auschwitz* are not forthcoming. We can also ultimately never be certain of the authenticity of Congo's seeming peripeteian anagnorisis of remorse (although Reestorff rightly points out that already the mere gesture of remorse is an acknowledgement of his killings as regrettable, 2015, 24–25). At this brief glance, TAOK's representational practices appear ethically indefensible.

However, Oppenheimer, his anonymous Indonesian co-director,¹¹ and co-director Christine Cynn draw on a vast array of filmic techniques to reframe and undermine the perpetrator's self-serving narratives. Lanzmann created a narrative frame of the barbershop scene as genuine and thereby reinforced the implied audience's empathic identification with Bomba's deeply emotional testimony. To the contrary, Oppenheimer frames the perpetrators' reenactments and narratives as unreliable by training his cameras on those of the perpetrators, juxtapositions in editing, and critical questions posed from the offscreen. In this distancing, TAOK's approach to perpetrators can be compared to Lanzmann's secret filming of Holocaust perpetrator testimonies or even, as in the case of Suchomel's seemingly cheerful singing of the "Treblinkalied" (McGlothlin 2020), perpetrator reenactment. Here, the sustained display of the secrecy of filming perpetrators—the secret camera van recurs numerous times in perpetrator interviews—vouches for the authenticity of the perpetrator testimony but crucially also functions as a distancing device continually reminding viewers that the ethical contexts operating offscreen, behind the secret cameras, are very different from those in front of the cameras where unsuspecting perpetrators believe they can speak and, indeed, sing uninhibited by the moral reproach of others. Lanzmann, too, uses the specular display of the camera to distance the normative world of the perpetrators. However, the offscreen ethical contexts surrounding the 1965-66 massacres in Indonesia, which validate the heroism of the killers, do not substantially differ from the normative world of the perpetrators fashioning themselves as heroic killers. This is not least because the killings have little public visibility (government propaganda films legitimizing the killings focus on the supposed brutality of communists). Hence, reenacting the perpetration in Indonesia gives a "re-visibility of the lost instances of death" (Wijaya 2016, 83) and "dissolves [the perpetrators's power] at the moment their performance is condensed onto tape and taken away from them, beyond their control" (Oppenheimer and Uwemedimo 2009, 102). Through the second-level camera, trained on the (diegetic) cameras of the perpetrators, TAOK can then, similar to Panh's confrontation of Khmer Rouge propaganda, draw the audience's attention towards the constructedness of the perpetrators' narratives and reenactments. Thus, we see perpetrators joyfully selecting outfits as if they are shooting an entertainment film, rehearsing their murderous performances in different movie genres, and directing each other's acting. Thereby, TAOK manages to continually expose the perpetrators' contradictions (e.g. calling themselves "cruel" but later "humane" killers), their overt discounting of victim perspectives (Suryono's testimony of victimization is spurned by the perpetrators' cameras but captured by Oppenheimer's; Nichols 2016, 178), their happy memories of raping teenage girls (expressed by Safit Pardede), their lack of guilt

¹¹ It should be noted that the Indonesian co-director and crew members chose to remain anonymous over fears of negative repercussions in Indonesia for their involvement in a film that undermines official government narratives.

and blatant disregard for human rights (shown by Adi Zulkadry), and the untruthfulness of Indonesia's main propaganda film justifying the killings while their own reenactments tap these same justificatory national narratives (as emerges from a discussion between Zulkadry and Congo especially in the director's cut) (Koch 2022, 6–12).

Perhaps most crucially, TAOK makes us aware of the double standards of their conscience, when it juxtaposes two redemption scenes, one showing Congo's seeming remorse at a killing site, and the other, appearing in excerpts several times throughout the film before being shown in full, an imagined reenactment of his victims who thank and decorate him with a medal for having killed and sent them to heaven (Koch 2022, 12–14). It is the former redemption scene upon whose credibility critics hinge the film's success or failure, while paying insufficient attention to the latter which structures both the cinematic and director's cut of the film. Oppenheimer and his editor's (Niels Pagh Anderson) self-reflexive editing of these two scenes patently call into question Congo's reliability. Which view on the killings should the audience believe? That Congo regrets the killings or that he believes them to be praiseworthy? Importantly, the reliability in question is less concerned with the fact/fiction divide most critics focus on, but rather with the ethicality of the perpetrators' perspective—a scene in heaven where Congo apologizes to his victims would be equally fictional but ethically less reprehensible than one in which he makes victims thank him. Ultimately, the truth the film is concerned with is less to do with fact and more to do with ethics.

Unlike all the other cases of reenactments discussed, the reenactments in TAOK stand out for their unreliability—and highlighting especially their ethical unreliability is precisely the point of TAOK. While the most common use of reenactments in documentaries on genocide is to directly facilitate access to truth, the perpetrator reenactments in TAOK serve this purpose inadvertently. Through TAOK's framing of the reenactments, it controverts their initial purpose of glorifying the perpetrators. TAOK lays bare the perpetrators construction of history—a construction shared with official Indonesian narratives—and ultimately calls for engaging with a violent past whose truth has long been denied.

Conclusion

That documentaries on genocide seek to establish a discourse of truth is unsurprising. Perhaps more surprising, however, is the role the reenactments play in service of these respective notions of truth. In contrast to commonly evoked binaries between reenactment and archive or reenactment and fiction, reenactments play a multifaceted role in what ultimately is a documentary quest for truth. They can, as in *Shoah*, create an affectively immersive scene that brings the viewer closer to the survivor's suffering—an aspect of representing genocide that escapes the archive and historical explanation of expository documentaries, even when they try to recapture an individual sense of the suffering through their interviews of survivors. But reenactments, their constructed status notwithstanding, can also serve to complement the archive in establishing historical truth, as in *Auschwitz*. The reenactments here were typically used when archival footage was not available and thus enabled a historically accurate visual reconstruction of facts. The fact that *Auschwitz* always discloses the reconstructed status of the reenactments through stylistic devices (color saturation, higher resolution etc.), so that they are not confused with archival material, just further supports the documentary's factual mission in that it points to the reenactments' evidentiary status as historically informed reconstruction rather than primary source. Used to different ends in *The Missing Picture* and TAOK, reenactments can also impugn the undisputed status of the archive's authenticity by “querying the stability and veracity of the original enactments”—and yet their purpose in doing so is

not to affirm “that there is no such thing as a fixed and stable truth” (Bruzzi 2020, 209 & 223). To the contrary, in documentaries on genocide, reenactments are seen and often even originate from a vantage point of truth to which viewers gain access through the documentary. Whether in the powerful reincarnation of suffering by members of the *Sonderkommando* in *Shoah*, in providing alternative images missing from propaganda in *The Missing Picture* or contesting entire historical narratives dominated by the perpetrators’ ethically problematic perspectives in *TAOK*, or even in displaying the pedestrian mundanity of thinking about murder methods by Nazi officials in *Auschwitz*—the notion of truth underlying reenactments in the context of genocide is not merely determined by a correspondence to fact, the traditional guarantor of truth, but is inextricable from ethics and affect. Reenactments thus must play an integral role in our discussions of how we come to grapple with violent pasts and how genocide can and should be represented.

Reenactments in documentaries on genocide are intricately linked to a notion of truth. This notion of truth is not simply established by an image’s supposed indexical link to an event—an indexical relation which reenactments would inevitably lack. Instead, reenactments in documentaries on genocide confront us with the integral operation in all historical endeavor: interpretation (Jay 1992). The constructedness of reenactments acknowledge the interpretative nature of historical narrative, which the concatenation of archival footage with its prioritization of indexicality often occludes even while its index of the event does not guarantee the truth of the interpretation of history its showing facilitates. It is reenactment’s active interpretive endeavor which enables it to be truthful.

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